

STAKEHOLDERS' LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS DISTANCE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The abrupt educational shift brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic compelled schools to adopt distance learning as an alternative mode of instructional delivery. In the Guindulman District, public schools implemented modular distance learning, requiring teachers, parents, and learners to assume new roles in the teaching–learning process. This study determined the stakeholders' level of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction towards distance learning during School Year 2021–2022. Guided by a descriptive-survey research design, the study involved 420 respondents composed of 84 teachers, 168 parents, and 168 learners selected through convenience sampling. Data were gathered using a researcher-developed questionnaire consisting of four parts: demographic profile, level of knowledge, attitude (affective, cognitive, and behavioral domains), and level of satisfaction (teacher performance, interaction, and learning assessment). Descriptive statistics, analysis of variance (ANOVA), and Pearson correlation were used to treat the data. Findings revealed that stakeholders were highly knowledgeable about distance learning policies, processes, and mechanisms. Their attitude toward distance learning was generally somehow positive across affective and cognitive aspects and strongly positive in terms of behavior, indicating willingness to support and participate in the modality. Stakeholders were very satisfied with teachers' performance, interaction practices, and learning assessment under modular distance learning. Results further showed significant differences in the levels of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction when grouped according to stakeholder category. A significant positive relationship was found between stakeholders' level of knowledge and attitude, as well as between attitude and satisfaction. These results underscore the importance of continuous orientation, support

systems, and stakeholder engagement to sustain effective implementation of distance learning in basic education.

Keywords: *Distance learning, Modular distance learning, Stakeholders' knowledge, Attitude, Satisfaction, and Basic education*

INTRODUCTION

The enormous challenges and changes resulting from the ongoing health crisis compelled the educational agencies to implement Distance Learning. There are three types of this, but Modular Distance Learning (MDL) has been the number one alternative form of learning delivery in the Philippines, given that it is the most preferred among all the other options of delivery modalities laid down by the Department of Education for the enrollees to choose from; feasible and applicable to the majority of learners; and at the same time, by the Covid-19 health restrictions and protocols.

Although DepEd appreciates and recognizes the value of distance learning during these trying times, implementing it is apparently demanding of time and energy on the part of the parents, tedious for the learners, and physically draining for the teachers. This had been instantaneously introduced to the parents and learners, enforced by the unprecedented situation. On the other hand, the teachers were utterly dismayed by the drastic changes in their way of teaching. Due to the sudden shift of events without any heads-up or ample time for preparation, some stakeholders might have developed a negative attitude towards Distance Learning that consequently may affect their level of satisfaction with its usage.

Distance learning has raised important questions about the determining factors influencing learning, satisfaction, and retention of the learners of this academic program. A key concern for most institutions and teachers is whether learners are satisfied with their learning experience. Hence, there is a need to study more in-depth distance education to overcome challenges and issues and identify factors influencing student satisfaction (Amoozegar et al., 2018).

In the study by Ahmed (2021), it was found that the parents' attitude was particularly sharp and negative towards distance learning; most of them were not satisfied with the distance learning process because they had to be at home during quarantine, where the unemployed, poor financial situation in addition to staying home with their children and watching the distance learning process.

Another study from Bordeos (2021) revealed the students' negative attitude toward Modular Distance Learning; they perceived it as having a negative effect on their learning experience and, therefore, were unsatisfied. However, in the study of Yayen and Labaria (2021), the teachers of Bataraza District I are said to be on a neutral or average level of perception, confidence, satisfaction, and experiences in modular distance learning.

Based on these studies, it is quite intriguing why these stakeholders differ in attitude and satisfaction towards distance learning when they all play similar crucial roles in its implementation. Other researchers claim that many factors could affect one's attitude towards something. Therefore, it can be presumed that lack of knowledge can be one factor that affects one's negative attitude towards distance learning.

Trovela (2021) analyzed the data from the interview of parents, and it was inferred that most of the parent participants' understanding of modular distance learning is the use of modules, mostly of written works that learners will answer at home. This simple answer only implies how minimal their knowledge is about the new learning modality. It was also inferred that their perception of modular distance learning poses challenges; as supported by their answers, it is quite difficult for them in the aspect of Education.

Since the implementation of distance learning has a lot to do with teacher's assistance, parental involvement, and learner participation, it is indispensable to view the teachers, parents, and learners' status and undertakings as important matters to look closely into when it comes to assessing the overall teaching and learning experience. For this reason and the studies mentioned above, the researcher was compelled to determine the stakeholders' level of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction towards distance learning to respond to the world's pressing occurrence.

Research Questions

The overall objective of this research was to determine the stakeholders' level of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction towards distance learning implemented in the public schools of Guindulman District during the school year 2021-2022.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.4 years of teaching experience?
2. What is the profile of the parent-respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 age;
 - 2.2 sex;
 - 2.3 highest level of education; and
 - 2.4 employment?
3. What is the profile of the learner-respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1 age;
 - 3.2 sex; and
 - 3.3 grade level?
4. What is the respondents' level of knowledge towards Distance Learning?
5. What is the respondents' attitude toward Distance Learning as to:
 - 5.1 affective domain;

- 5.2 cognitive domain; and
- 5.3 behavior domain?
- 6. What is the respondents' level of satisfaction in the implementation of Distance Learning in terms of:
 - 6.1 teacher's performance
 - 6.2 interaction; and
 - 6.3 learning assessment?
- 7. Is there a significant difference between the stakeholders:
 - 7.1 level of knowledge;
 - 7.2 attitude; and
 - 7.3 satisfaction towards distance learning?
- 8. Is there a significant relationship between the stakeholders:
 - 8.1 level of knowledge and their attitude; and
 - 8.2 attitude and their level of satisfaction towards distance learning?
- 9. What action plan can be proposed from the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research utilized Descriptive-Survey Design which represented the facts concerning the teachers, parents, and learners' demographic profile, their level of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction towards distance learning. This method also was comparatively time-saving and had the benefit of collecting responses from a large group of subjects at a relatively low cost (Dahlberg and McCaig 2010). Gay (1997) asserts that descriptive-survey design involves data collection to answer questions concerning the status of the subject of study.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the public schools of the Guindulman District under the Department of Education, Division of Bohol, located in the eastern part of the province. Teachers, parents, and learners served as respondents, representing the key stakeholders directly involved in school operations and the learning process. This district was chosen because its diverse school communities provided relevant insights for assessing the conditions and experiences central to the study. Pilot testing was carried out among selected respondents from various grade levels to ensure the clarity and reliability of the research instrument.

Research Participants

There were a total of four hundred twenty (420) respondents comprising one hundred sixty-eight (168) of each selected parents and learners and eighty-four (84) teachers who were politely asked to take part as key participants in the study. The convenience sampling method was adopted to select samples from the target population.

Convenience sampling is a nonprobability or nonrandom sampling where members of the target population meet certain practical criteria (Etikan, Musa & Alkassim, 2015).

Research Instrument

This study gathered data via a survey questionnaire. The research tool had four parts: Part I. (Respondents' Demographic Profile) and Part II. (Level of Knowledge towards Distance Learning), Part III. (Attitude towards Distance Learning), and Part IV is the Satisfaction towards Distance Learning.

Part I has the teachers, parents, and learners' demographic profiles. Part II contained 15 questions extracted from DepEd Order No. 018, s. 2020 and DepEd Order No. 032, s. 2020 that measured the stakeholders' level of knowledge towards distance learning. Part III has 21 items that measured the stakeholders' attitude towards distance learning concerning three domains/sections: cognitive, affective, and behavioral. The questions on this part were modified based on a set of questionnaires developed by Javier (2020).

Lastly, Part IV has 18 items that comprised questions related to the level of satisfaction of the stakeholders towards distance learning in terms of Teacher's Performance (6), Interaction (6), and Learning Assessment (6), whose constructs and questions were also adapted from the questionnaires used in the study of Ali and Ahmad (2011) and Fieger (2012).

The survey questionnaire used a 4-point Likert scale, was designed to suit the research objectives, and had been pilot-tested in another public school named San Isidro Elementary School in San Isidro, Candijay, Bohol for validity and readability.

Research Procedure

To conduct this study, the researcher first obtained approval from the Campus Director and the Dean of the College of Advanced Studies, as well as authorization from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education in the province of Bohol, Guindulman District Supervisor, and the School Heads of each public school.

Following this, the researcher personally went to each school and distributed the questionnaires to the respondents with the help of the school heads. In doing this, the researcher adhered to the health constraints and guidelines. The respondents were given three to four weeks to complete the questionnaire. Then, the data were collected, tallied, tabulated, and collated before being analyzed and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Statistical Treatment

To identify the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment, years of experience, and designation, percentages were computed.

To determine the extent of occupational health hazard exposure and the level of protective practices, the weighted mean formula was applied.

To test for significant differences in the protective practices of the respondents when grouped according to their profile, a one-way ANOVA was utilized.

Finally, to examine the significant relationship between occupational health hazard exposure and protective practices, the Pearson correlation coefficient was employed.

RESULTS

The data were collected from respondents through survey questionnaires and are presented in tabular form for clarity and ease of interpretation.

Table 1. Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

1.1 Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
21-30 years old	13	15.48	3.5
31-40 years old	25	29.76	2
41-50 years old	32	38.09	1
51-60 years old	13	15.48	3.5
61 years old and above	1	1.19	5
Total	84	100%	
1.2 Sex			
Male	18	21.43	2
Female	66	78.57	1
Total	84	100%	
1.3 Highest Educational Attainment			
Bachelor Degree Holder	33	39.29	2
With units in Master's Degree	47	55.95	1
Masters' Degree Graduate	4	4.76	3
With Ph.D./ Ed. D. units	0	0.00	
Doctorate	0	0.00	
Total	84	100%	
1.4 Years of Teaching Experience			
5 years and below	17	20.24	2
6-10 years	24	28.56	1
11-15 years	15	17.86	3
16-20 years	14	16.67	4.5
21 years and above	14	16.67	4.5
Total	84	100%	

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents. The results show that the teacher-respondents who fall in the age bracket of 41-50 years old have a percentage of 38.09%, making them first in rank. This was followed by teachers who belong to the age group of 31-40 years old, which have the frequency of 25 (29.76%); Next are teachers whose age are between 21-30 years old and 51-60 years old with the

same percentage of 15.48%; meanwhile, teachers who are 61 years old and above got the lowest frequency of 1 (1.19%). The sex distribution shows that the majority (78.57%) were females, while only 18 (21.43%) were males. Olaivar (2016), as cited by Golosino (2019), inferred that the teaching profession is more appealing to females than males.

With regards to the highest educational attainment of the respondents, 47 (38.09%) of the teachers attained units in Master's Degree; 33 (39.29%) were Bachelor's Degree Holder, and 4 (4.76%) were Master's Degree graduates. None of the respondents attained Ph.D./Ed. D. units or doctorate. The result implies that the teachers are still in the process of finishing their master's degrees.

In terms of years in service, 24 teachers (28.56%) served for 6-10 years; 17 teachers (20.24%) were in the teaching service for just five years and below; 15 teachers (17.86%) have 11-15 years; and 14 for both 16-20 years and 21 years and above with the lowest percentage of 16.67%. As drawn from the results, it can be inferred that the study locale has more novice to distinguished teachers than expert teachers.

Table 2. Profile of the Parent-Respondents

2.1 Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
30 years old and below	18	10.71	4
31-40 years old	62	36.91	1
41-50 years old	56	33.33	2
51 years old and above	32	19.05	3
Total	168	100%	
2.2 Sex			
Male	48	28.57	2
Female	120	71.43	1
Total	168	100%	
2.3 Educational Attainment			
Elementary Level/Graduate	21	12.50	5
High School Level	31	18.45	3
High School Graduate	59	35.12	1
College Level	32	19.05	2
Bachelor's Degree Holder	25	14.88	4
Total	168	100%	
2.4 Employment			
Unemployed	100	59.52	1
Self-employed	30	17.86	2
Private Employee	9	5.36	4
Government Employee	28	16.66	3
Business owner/entrepreneur	1	0.60	5
Total	168	100%	

Table 2 shows the results of the demographic profile of the parent-respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, and employment. The results show that many

parent-respondents fall in the age group of 31-40 years old with a percentage of 36.91%, and the least represented are parents younger than 30 years old (10.71%).

There were 120 females (71.43%) and 48 males (28.57%), which revealed that females outnumbered males. In their educational attainment, a relatively small number of 12.50% of participants have finished elementary school; 59 (35.12%) of them completed secondary school; 19.05% are college undergraduates, 18.45% are high school undergraduates; while the remaining 14.88% are bachelor's degree holder. The result implied a low success rate of completing education among the parent-respondents.

The respondents' demographic profile in terms of employment shows that unemployment among parents has the highest percentage of 59.52%, followed by parents who are self-employed in the second rank (17.86%), then government employees in the third rank (16.66%). Next are parents working for a private company (5.36%), and lastly, the Business owner/entrepreneur, ranked last (0.60%). The data results generally reveal that most parent-respondents were not successful in finishing their studies; that being the case, they are leaning more towards unemployment.

As shown in the table, several parents are employed, but it can also mean they would not have time to be present during the distance learning of their child, for they have to be at work. Some of the parents are working outside their homes during the daytime, which leaves no one to guide/teach the learner. Being tired all day, they are not motivated to help either because of too many activities that need to be accomplished in the given modules (Bayucca, 2021).

Table 3. Profile of the Learner-Respondents

3.1 Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
9 – 10 years old	59	35.12	2
11 – 12 years old	66	39.29	1
13 – 14 years old	20	11.90	4
15 years old and above	23	13.69	3
Total	168	100%	
3.2 Sex			
Male	63	37.50	2
Female	105	62.50	1
Total	168	100%	
3.3 Grade Level			
Elementary (Grades 4 – 6 learners)	116	69.05	1
Junior High School (Grades 7 – 10 learners)	52	30.95	2
Total	168	100%	

Table 3 showcases the learner-respondents profile in terms of age, sex, and grade level. It revealed that out of 168 learner-respondents, 66 belonged to the age bracket of 11-12 years old (39.29%). This was followed by learners whose ages fall under the age bracket of 9-10 years old (35.12%), then 15 years old and above (13.69%). Meanwhile,

learners who are 13-14 years old came last in rank with a frequency of twenty (20) or (11.90%).

As to learners' sex, data revealed that females outnumbered males with the frequency of 105 (62.50%) and 63 (37.50%), respectively. This was attested by Gumba (2013), as cited by Hernandez and Cudiamat (2018), who stressed that in almost every aspect of the Philippine educational system, women and girls outnumber men and boys. The same table shows that the majority of learner-respondents represented elementary learners (grade 4-6) and followed by Junior High School (Grades 7-10) learners with a frequency of 116 or (69.05%) and 52 or (30.95%), respectively.

Table 4. Respondent's Assessment on the Stakeholders' Level of Knowledge Towards Distance Learning

Statement	Teachers		Parents		Learners		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	Rank
As a teacher/parent/learner, I know that...									
1. the self-learning modules are anchored in Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS).	3.82	SA	3.19	A	3.29	SA	3.43	SA	6
2. the learning materials can be organized and presented in digital/printed format.	3.70	SA	3.29	SA	3.29	SA	3.43	SA	6
3. Any family member may be a facilitator of learning at home.	3.70	SA	3.29	SA	3.40	SA	3.46	SA	4
4. self-learning modules will be delivered to the learners through schools that are located in coastal areas, far-flung provinces, and communities	3.57	SA	3.20	A	3.29	SA	3.35	SA	12.5
5. in distance learning, you can ask for the teacher's assistance through call or text	3.81	SA	3.49	SA	3.43	SA	3.58	SA	1
6. the teacher shall do home visits to learners needing remediation or assistance	3.56	SA	3.30	SA	3.42	SA	3.43	SA	6
7. distance learning occurs between the teacher and the learners who are geographically remote from each other during instruction.	3.45	SA	3.23	A	3.42	SA	3.37	SA	10.5
8. printed modules will be delivered to the learners or picked up by their parents at designated areas within agreed schedules.	3.79	SA	3.36	SA	3.42	SA	3.52	SA	3
9. students who have access to the internet can use the department's DepEd Commons, an online education platform developed by the government agency to support alternative learning modes.	3.51	SA	3.27	SA	3.39	SA	3.39	SA	9
10. DepEd had government-run television and radio stations as platforms for delivering lessons during the pandemic	3.56	SA	3.27	SA	3.43	SA	3.42	SA	8
11. the pupils' grades are generated from there: (1) summative tests or called "written works," and (2) performance assessment which is called "performance outputs."	3.68	SA	3.40	SA	3.51	SA	3.53	SA	2
12. unauthorized printing, uploading, and conducting activities involving sharing digital files other than the intended purpose are strictly prohibited.	3.62	SA	3.17	A	3.33	SA	3.37	SA	10.5
13. schools whose majority of learners do not have a household member or any responsible adult to provide instructional support and facilitate distance learning may hire Learning Support Aides	3.42	SA	3.03	A	3.24	A	3.23	A	15
14. one of the functions of a learning support aide or LSA is assisting in the production and reproduction of modules, activity sheets, and other instructional materials	3.57	SA	3.26	SA	3.23	A	3.35	SA	12.5
15. learners who cannot manage independent learning, including learners with disabilities and special needs, will be prioritized in the deployment of Learning Support Aides	3.48	SA	3.21	A	3.29	SA	3.33	SA	14

Weighted Mean (WM)	3.62	SA	3.26	SA	3.36	SA	3.41	SA (Highly Knowledgeable)
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Legend:

3.25 - 4.00

Strongly Agree (SA) - Highly Knowledgeable

1.75 - 2.49

Disagree (D) - Fairly Knowledgeable

2.50 - 3.24

Agree (A) - Moderately Knowledgeable

1.00 - 1.74

Strongly Disagree (SD) - Showing No Knowledge

Table 4 illustrates the stakeholders' level of knowledge of the distance learning delivery modality. The table shows that item 5, "in distance learning, you can ask for the teacher's assistance through call or text," got the highest weighted mean of 3.58, interpreted as 'Strongly Agree.'

The result denotes that the stakeholders have been oriented on how to digitally communicate and interact with one another despite being geographically apart in distance learning. In addition, teachers are aware of their responsibility to attend to the concerns of the parent or the learner via call or text.

On the other hand, item number 13, "schools whose majority of learners do not have a household member or any responsible adult to provide instructional support and facilitate distance learning, may hire Learning Support Aides," ranked at the bottom with the weighted mean of 3.23 interpreted as 'Agree.' The result indicates that most of the stakeholders know about this privilege of hiring Learning Support Aides, but there are some who do not.

In DepEd Order No. 018, s. 2020, it was stated that communities/barangays/schools with a higher number of learners or households needing support should be prioritized in the deployment of Learning Support Aides. However, the SDOs will still evaluate and approve the request based on the school's analysis of the educational landscape following the guidelines set in the order and the gathered information on the learner and household profile.

Although this is nothing compared to the good overall result of the stakeholders' level of knowledge towards distance learning with a general weighted mean of 3.41, which is interpreted as 'highly knowledgeable.' People who do not entirely know what they are entitled to in distance learning can be given an orientation to educate them more about what they can do to maximize their time and resources. If worst-case scenario, COVID-19 thrives, and the distance learning delivery modality continues.

Moreover, the data result implies that the stakeholders of Guindulman District know what distance learning is, how it works, and the policy guidelines that come with it. They have most likely read the DepEd memorandum to take part in the implementation of distance learning. This further shows that the stakeholders cooperate in the new normal education system.

Table 5.1. Respondent's Assessment of the Stakeholders' Attitude Towards Distance Learning as to Affective Aspect

Statement	Teachers		Parents		Learners		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	Rank
1. enjoy facilitating/using the digital and printed self-learning materials that are used for remote teaching	3.43	SA	2.94	A	3.35	SA	3.24	A	3
2. find assisting my child in answering their self-learning materials as a pleasurable experience.	3.51	SA	3.13	A	3.28	SA	3.31	SA	1
3. feel excited when the teacher administers modular learning assessments to my child	3.40	SA	3.07	A	3.21	A	3.23	A	4
4. think it's fascinating that the teacher monitors my child's learning progress using various kinds of communication	3.45	SA	3.11	A	3.28	SA	3.28	SA	2
5. believe that it is possible to assess my child's performance/product-based outputs through modules.	3.29	SD	2.83	A	2.94	A	3.02	A	5
6. think that doing modular distance learning is a pleasurable and interesting procedure for my child's education.	2.81	D	2.68	A	2.83	A	2.77	A	7
7. like the use of modular distance learning to deliver the lesson to my child.	2.75	D	2.71	A	2.92	A	2.79	A	6
Weighted Mean (WM)	3.23	A	2.92	A	3.12	A	3.09	Agree (Somehow Positive)	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00

Strongly Agree (SA)

1.75 – 2.49

Disagree (DA)

2.50 – 3.24

Agree (A)

1.00 – 1.74

Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 5.1 illustrates the stakeholders' attitude toward distance learning and the respondents' practical aspect. Due to the emergence of COVID-19 in the Philippines, many changes happened in the educational landscape. One of these is the mode of instruction that the Department of Education implemented. The shift of the teaching-learning delivery in schools to modular distance learning made the delivery of basic quality education more challenging on the part of the school personnel (Castroverde & Acala, 2021).

It can be deduced from the table that item number 2, 'find assisting my child in answering his/her self-learning materials as a pleasurable experience,' got the highest weighted mean of 3.31, interpreted as 'Strongly Agree.' This means the parents enjoy assisting their child's learning at home.

This is because they can monitor their child's learning status and progress and, at the same time, will have the opportunity to bond with them. This is similar to the idiom, "hitting two birds with one stone." It will enable the parents to achieve two things, rather

than just one. Furthermore, this finding describes the parents' high level of interest in the ethical climate of distance learning and their readiness to accommodate this type of educational experience (Hamaidi et al., 2021).

As for the learners, answering the modules is to their liking. They are not forced nor coerced to finish the self-learning tasks but are given sufficient time to answer them. This is probably the reason why they enjoy the process of completing all the weekly learning assessments. On top of that, the learners learn at their own pace without any pressure of coping with their classmates, unlike in face-to-face classes wherein the teachers give time but are limited to what is feasible for the subject. Learning at home means having a flexible timeframe. The learner is ready to proceed at this own rate and recycle, if necessary, Goldschmid (1972) as cited by Bordeos (2021).

Besides, the teachers also find the printing of modules enjoyable. In implementing modular distance learning in the Division of Bohol, teachers were given ready-to-print modules and learning activity sheets. These materials were prepared by selected teachers across the division with expertise regarding the lesson contents. So, the teachers were not stressed in preparing materials for their students every week. They only must print these materials. Hence, they found it less stressful (Budiongan, 2020).

Meanwhile, item number 6, 'think that doing modular distance learning is pleasurable and interesting procedure for my child's learning,' got the lowest weighted mean of 2.77, interpreted as 'Agree.' This indicates that the parents and teachers ascertain that learners somehow find the distance learning delivery modality an interesting mode of instruction. Conceivably because this is their first time studying from home. Every transaction, from getting and returning the modules to taking assessments conveniently at home, is amusing and comfortable.

On the flip side of the coin, other extroverted and outdoorsy learners may find it grueling to be confined to a single area for learning. Garbe et al. (2020) affirmed this, and Rahiem (2021) stated that the first challenge—lack of learner motivation specifically related to remote learning—was applied to a response if it met the following inclusion criteria: the response indicated that the struggle was related to the shift to distance learning. This may have included a struggle with lack of social interaction, figuring out how to learn this way, and the student feeling like remote learning did not match learning style.

In general, the attitude of stakeholders towards distance learning as to affective aspect attained the average weighted mean of 2.99 (Agree). It can be inferred that the stakeholders have a good disposition towards distance learning and have already accepted the responsibilities of using it. Furthermore, this hints that the stakeholders have adjusted to the new normal education setup.

Table 5.2. Respondent's Assessment of the Stakeholders' Attitude Towards Distance Learning as to Cognitive Aspect

Statement	Teachers		Parents		Learners		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	Rank
As a teacher/parent/learner, I learn that...									
1. Distance Learning is engaging and stimulating.	3.02	A	2.75	A	3.08	A	2.95	A	4.5
2. Distance Learning is a viable alternative approach promising educational results better than face-to-face instruction.	2.77	A	2.68	A	2.86	A	2.77	A	7
3. answering digital and printed modules for distance learning is possible and doable.	3.21	A	3.00	A	3.17	A	3.13	A	1.5
4. self-learning modules are appealing, motivating, and engaging in both print and digital formats	3.05	A	2.73	A	3.06	A	2.95	A	4.5
5. I am given enough time to complete each weekly learning task without regard for my learning needs	2.90	A	2.80	A	3.05	A	2.92	A	6
6. more interaction between learners and teachers and among learners themselves is attained in distance learning	3.27	SA	2.93	A	3.18	A	3.13	A	1.5
7. pupils do not make more likely to cheat (e.g., plagiarism) in completing the learning tasks	3.44	SA	2.83	A	2.97	A	3.08	A	3
Weighted Mean (WM)	3.10	A	2.82	A	3.05	A	2.99	Agree (Somehow Positive)	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00
2.50 – 3.24

Strongly Agree (SA)
Agree (A)

1.75 – 2.49
1.00 – 1.74

Disagree (DA)
Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 5.2 illustrates the respondent's attitude towards distance learning delivery modality as to the cognitive aspect. The mental part of an attitude refers to how stakeholders think about or interpret remote learning as an alternative to face-to-face learning.

In this table, item number 3 'answering digital and/or printed modules for distance learning is possible and doable' and item number 6 'more interaction between learners and teachers and among learners themselves is attained in distance learning' both ranked first with a weighted mean of 3.13 (Agree).

This denotes that the learners perceive distance learning as attainable and manageable amidst the pandemic; parents also think they can facilitate their child at home, and teachers see distance learning as a practicable alternative form of instruction for face-to-face classes. Besides, the stakeholders believe there is more interaction happening in remote learning between learners and teachers and among learners

themselves than in normal types, which means they are initiating communication well enough.

Three (3) themes were brought up by Dargo and Dimas (2021), one of which revealed that having no interactive relationship between the teacher and the learners will lead the learners not to be interested to learn and refuse to explore their potential in their own. Learners cannot interact with their teacher to ask questions about their lesson, which leads to a lack of processing of the module's content and a lack of explanation from the teacher.

Nevertheless, it can be surmised that these teachers, learners, and parents were doing their best to keep each other informed about their activities and were continually communicating for the learners' benefit. After all, Distance learning will be doable and useful, especially during these trying times, as long as both parties make an effort to engage. With today's vast technologies, there can be no hindrance in terms of communication.

On the other hand, item 2, 'Distance Learning is a viable alternative approach promising educational result better than face to face instruction,' got the lowest weighted mean of 2.77 or 'Agree' as interpreted, which placed the lowest in rank. The result signifies that some stakeholders favor distance learning as having a more promising educational effect than face-to-face instruction, except for those remaining people who think that the mode of pre-pandemic instruction is still more effective and are still hoping for the normal face-to-face classes to restart. Most students wanted to come back face to face. Roy et al.'s (2020), as cited by Bordeos (2021), reported similar findings; the students preferred to return to face-to-face instruction post the COVID-19 lockdown.

Overall, the stakeholders' attitude towards distance learning in terms of cognitive aspect got the weighted mean of 2.99, which is interpreted as 'Agree' is a good thing. This means that they perceive distance learning as a useful instrument for continuing education.

Table 5.3. Respondent's Assessment of the Stakeholders' Attitude Towards Distance Learning as to Behavior Aspect

Statement	Teachers		Parents		Learners		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	Rank
1. support my child in their learning assessments as a means of evaluating learning needs and progress	3.50	SA	3.31	SA	3.29	SA	3.37	SA	4
2. seek for other supplemental learning materials which are close to having the essential learning competencies	3.57	SA	3.15	SA	3.30	SA	3.34	SA	6
3. facilitate my child in attaining the learning objectives that may be met by taking their learning potential into account	3.50	SA	3.21	SA	3.33	SA	3.35	SA	5
4. use the learning resources like textbooks, activity sheets, teacher-made	3.49	SA	3.28	SA	3.39	SA	3.39	SA	2.5

modules, etc. as supplements to the existing learning resources									
5. allot enough time guiding my child is undertaking a lesson or accomplishing an activity.	3.49	SA	3.23	SA	3.27	SA	3.33	SA	7
6. see that my child receives copies of the self-learning modules either in print or digital format.	3.65	SA	3.38	SA	3.29	SA	3.44	SA	1
7. maintain a healthy balance between my child's academic and socio-emotional aspects of learning	3.57	SA	3.24	SA	3.36	SA	3.39	SA	2.5
Weighted Mean (WM)	3.54	SA	3.26	SA	3.32	SA	3.37	Strongly Agree (Positive)	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00
2.50 – 3.24

Strongly Agree (SA)
Agree (A)

1.75 – 2.49
1.00 – 1.74

Disagree (DA)
Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 5.3 illustrates the respondent's attitude towards distance learning delivery modality as to behavior. Item number 6, 'see to it that my child receives copies of the self-learning modules either in print or digital format,' placed first in rank with the highest weight mean of 3.44, which is interpreted as 'Strongly Agree.' This means that the parents, teachers, and learners are all doing their part by ensuring they all have and provide copies of the self-learning modules. This further explains how the stakeholders take the initiative in distance learning which is commendable.

On the contrary, item 5 'allot enough time in guiding my child is undertaking a lesson or in accomplishing an activity got the least weighted mean of 3.33 or Strongly Agree. Despite being in the last rank, this is a favorable result. This reveals the parents' effort in sparing time to facilitate their child, and in the same way, the learner does his best in learning the lessons by devoting enough time to his studies.

The result shows congruence with the study of Palma et al. (2021), which found that modular learners received high academic support from their parents, and with the study of Liu et al. (2020), which revealed that students were likewise provided substantial parental academic support despite continuing their education during the pandemic.

This can be supported by the concept of guided participation by Lev Vygotsky, which highlights that cognitive development occurs in a social context while extending sociocultural theory beyond language-based dialogue. Importantly, guided participation builds on and extends Vygotsky's notion of ZPD. Rogoff (1990), as cited by Scott & Palincsar (2013), writes, "Children's cognitive development is an apprenticeship—it occurs through guided participation in social activity with companions who support and stretch children's understanding of and skill in using the tools of the culture.

Erlendsdóttir (2010), as cited by Tus (2021), referred to parental involvement as the amount of parental participation regarding schooling and a child's life. Treating children negatively, like physical abuse, yelling, and other punishments, negatively impact the children's academic performance and outputs. On the other hand, those students having an active parenting involvement in their education will likely motivate them and

lead them to success in the idea of making school more exciting and fulfilling in short-process for these students.

Generally, the stakeholders attained the general weighted mean of 3.37 or 'Strongly Agree.' This discloses that stakeholders have a positive attitude toward distance learning as to behavioral aspects and shows that they take on the challenges of investing time and effort in implementing distance learning as a fruitful and successful one.

Table 6.1. Respondent's Assessment of the Stakeholders' Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning as to Teachers' Performance

Statement	Teachers		Parents		Learners		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	Rank
The teacher...									
1. develops the self-learning modules as interesting and engaging as possible.	3.51	VS	3.41	VS	3.45	VS	3.46	VS	2
2. offers academic assistance to me regarding the topics found in modules.	3.49	VS	3.32	VS	3.42	VS	3.41	VS	5
3. has a clear and straightforward technique of disseminating important school announcements.	3.56	VS	3.30	VS	3.45	VS	3.44	VS	4
4. has a well-organized and systematized way of distributing and retrieving modules.	3.67	VS	3.47	VS	3.54	VS	3.56	VS	1
5. regularly monitors my child's learning progress through me.	3.60	VS	3.33	VS	3.42	VS	3.45	VS	3
6. provides additional learning materials apart from the existing modules for me to have more references in facilitating my child	3.43	VS	3.23	S	3.35	VS	3.34	VS	6
Weighted Mean (WM)	3.54	VS	3.34	VS	3.44	VS	3.44		Very Satisfied

Legend:

3.25 - 4.00
2.50 - 3.24

Very Satisfied (VS)
Satisfied (S)

1.75 - 2.49
1.00 - 1.74

Dissatisfied (DS)
Very Dissatisfied (VDS)

Table 6.1 exposes the respondents' assessment of satisfaction with distance learning delivery modality as to Teacher's Performance. In this study, the teacher's performance is an operational definition of the teacher's strategies and undertakings in making the modular distance learning delivery modality convenient and useful for both parents and learners.

The table reveals that item 4 'has a well-organized and systematized way of distributing and retrieving modules' got the highest weighted mean of 3.56, interpreted as 'Very Satisfied.' This implies that the parents and learners are satisfied with how the teacher organizes, distributes, and retrieves the self-learning materials. In the same way, the teachers find it satisfying to have an organized and systematized way of doing things in distance learning.

One of the benefits of being organized at work is increased productivity. Keeping organized will save time looking for things and have more time to work on important tasks as an organization can improve the flow of communication between both factions. After

all, better communication leads to better results (Monster Worldwide, 2022). This is true and evident for the stakeholders since they are satisfied with how things are executed in their schools.

On the other hand, the indicator that 'provides additional learning materials apart from the existing modules for me to have more references in facilitating my child' was placed last in rank with a weighted mean of 3.34. Although lowest in rank, this is still interpreted as 'Very Satisfied.' From the results, it can be deduced that the teachers are giving their all in providing the best possible learning materials for the learners and for the parents to have more references in teaching their child. Indeed, teachers' resourcefulness is tested in distance learning. They must ensure they can break the geographical distance between them and their students (Budiongan, 2020).

Overall, the weighted mean of the stakeholders' satisfaction in distance learning delivery in terms of teacher's performance was 3.44 with a verbal description of 'Very Satisfied,' which means that they feel satisfied with the teacher's performance in distance learning. El-Kassas (1991), as cited by Wahab and Iskandar (2020), defines performance as the fulfillment of an obligation in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract. In other words, it is an actual result achieved by someone carrying out their duties.

Teachers wear many hats, and their performance matters because they play a crucial role in educating the minds of the young. This conformed to Nacar (2021) when she stressed that teachers are taking on new roles in schools and their profession and rethinking their primary responsibility as directors of student learning. They collaborate with colleagues, families, politicians, academics, community members, employers, and others to set clear and achievable knowledge, skills, and values.

Table 6.2. Respondent's Assessment on the Stakeholders' Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning as to Teachers' Interaction

Statement	Teachers		Parents		Learners		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	Rank
The teacher...									
1. attends to my concerns regarding the lessons via call or text.	3.69	VS	3.35	VS	3.42	VS	3.49	VS	1.5
2. visits my child struggling in their studies to extend academic assistance further.	3.48	VS	3.26	VS	3.24	S	3.33	VS	6
3. uses a familiar and convenient means of communication like a messenger.	3.67	VS	3.42	VS	3.37	VS	3.49	VS	1.5
4. checks on the learners' holistic well-being via call or text.	3.54	VS	3.36	VS	3.39	VS	3.43	VS	4.5
5. provides me with other options on how to approach or contact them when I have questions about the modules	3.60	VS	3.37	VS	3.31	VS	3.43	VS	4.5

6. communicates with me and asks about my child's learning status and performance.	3.61	VS	3.40	VS	3.42	VS	3.48	VS	3
Weighted Mean (WM)	3.60	VS	3.36	VS	3.36	VS	3.44	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

3.25 - 4.00

Very Satisfied (VS)

1.75 - 2.49

Dissatisfied (DS)

2.50 - 3.24

Satisfied (S)

1.00 - 1.74

Very Dissatisfied (VDS)

It can be gleaned in table 6.2 the respondents' assessment of satisfaction towards distance learning delivery modality as to Interaction. Interaction is defined in this study as the amount of interactivity among the teachers, learners, and parents.

Item number 1 'attends to my concerns regarding the lessons via call or text,' and 3 'uses a familiar and convenient means of communication like messenger' are in the first rank, having the same weighted mean of 3.49 or Very Satisfied. This means that the teachers are doing an excellent job of sustaining the open communication between them and the parents and learners. They are tech-savvy enough to use social media platforms like a messenger to keep track of the learners' status.

The quality of interaction in distance learning education has been steadily increasing with the advancements in communication technologies from the printing press to radio, television, satellite, and especially the Internet (Terzi & Celik, 2005). This upholds the result wherein stakeholders integrate technology into their daily life undertakings and education.

In addition, studies have found that teacher-student interaction is one of the greatest contributors to students' motivation and satisfaction and their ability to cope with learning assignments. As distance learning has become widespread and inevitable in times of emergency or crisis, which may occur again in the future, improving interaction during distance learning in an emergency is very important. This may improve the learners' ability to maintain their regular learning routine despite crises (Sason & Kellerman, 2021). Teachers who take the time to have quality individual interactions with their students also increase the student's sense of a supportive environment and satisfaction (McWherter, 2012).

On the contrary, item number 2, 'visits my child who is struggling in his/her studies to extend further academic assistance,' got the lowest weighted mean of 3.33, yet is still interpreted as Very Satisfied'. Despite being busy with lots of paperwork, this proves that the teachers still find ways to serve the learners. Also, In DepEd Order No. 032, s. 2020, it was underscored that teachers must extend academic assistance at home to those learners who are having setbacks with their schooling. Additionally, this shows that teachers are adhering to the policy guidelines prescribed by the Department of Education.

In summary, the respondents were given an average weighted mean of 3.44 or Very Satisfied as described. This denotes those stakeholders are contented with the

teacher's determined attempt to initiate interaction between them, the parents, and the learners.

DeBourgh (1999) opined that when teachers use effective pedagogy, technology can facilitate interactive instruction and communication without compromising satisfaction with the instructor, education, or the course. Overall course satisfaction is related to overall ratings of the instructor and teaching, regardless of course format, the physical separation of participants, or technology-mediation of communication and interaction. Satisfaction in distance-education courses is related to the instructor's performance--just as in traditional face-to-face classes.

Table 6.3. Respondent's Assessment of the Stakeholders' Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning as to Learning Assessment

Statement	Teachers		Parents		Learners		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	WM	DI	Rank
The teacher...									
1. creates learning activity sheets or LAS that are suited and appropriate to assess the pupils' learning.	3.62	VS	3.48	VS	3.52	VS	3.54	VS	3
2. administers the summative tests at appropriate schedules.	3.62	VS	3.56	VS	3.51	VS	3.56	VS	1
3. employs fair and honest evaluation procedures in assessing my child's learning	3.62	VS	3.52	VS	3.49	VS	3.54	VS	3
4. gives clear and useful feedback on my child's learning performance and accomplishments.	3.62	VS	3.45	VS	3.55	VS	3.54	VS	3
5. utilizes reliable and valid criteria in evaluating my child's performance and product-based outputs	3.55	VS	3.41	VS	3.39	VS	3.45	VS	6
6. gives my child an adequate timeframe to accomplish his/her weekly learning tasks.	3.55	VS	3.49	VS	3.51	VS	3.52	VS	5
Weighted Mean (WM)	3.60	VS	3.48	VS	3.49	VS	3.52	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

3.25 - 4.00
2.50 - 3.24

Very Satisfied (VS)
Satisfied (S)

1.75 - 2.49
1.00 - 1.74

Dissatisfied (DS)
Very Dissatisfied (VDS)

Table 6.3 reveals the respondent's assessment of Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning as to Learning Assessment. This term refers to the teacher's modified ways of evaluating learning performance in distance learning.

Item number 2 'administers the summative tests at appropriate schedules' ranked first with the highest weighted mean of 3.56 or Very Satisfied as interpreted. This conveys the teacher's promptness in managing the schedules of summative tests as learning assessments. Therefore, the parents and learners are very satisfied with the scheduling of summative tests.

In this context, it is just right and just that the teachers administer the summative tests at appropriate schedules for the learners also need to prepare for it. With a lack of preparation, their test results might not be as good compared to being ready for such an activity.

Meanwhile, item number 5, 'utilizes reliable and valid criteria in evaluating my child's performance and product-based outputs,' was ranked last with the weighted mean of 3.45, interpreted as Very Satisfied. This tells how the parents and learners are grunted with the teacher's standards that are used for measuring the learners' learning status and progress. It further explains that learners feel that the criteria for judging their performances or outputs are reasonable and viable. This can motivate the learners to achieve their standards and recognize their attainability.

In general, the stakeholders' assessment of satisfaction towards distance learning in terms of learning assessment got an average weighted mean of 3.52, which indicates they are very satisfied with the learning assessments. Students' perceptions of their assessment can influence their adopted learning approach. Students' general orientation toward learning can be described as either 'deep' (transformational) or 'shallow' (reproductive) orientation; transformational learning techniques are more likely to result in higher levels of achievement and student satisfaction than reproductive techniques (Scouller & Prosser, 1994).

Table 7.1. Test of Difference Between the Stakeholders' Level of Knowledge Towards Distance Learning

Variable	F	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Stakeholders' Level of Knowledge Towards Distance Learning	16.943	2, 417	<.001	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Difference is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)*

Post hoc comparisons indicated that among the perception of the respondents, teachers' level of knowledge towards distance learning (M = 3.616, SD = 0.305) is significantly different compared to that of the parents (M = 3.358, SD = 0.461) and learners (M = 3.263, SD = 0.509). This denotes that the difference lies between parents and learners, and teachers.

Post Hoc Comparisons

Variable	Respondents		Mean Difference	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Stakeholders' Level of Knowledge Towards Distance Learning	Parents	Teachers	0.353	<.001	Significant	Reject H ₀
		Learners	0.095	0.158	Not Significant	Do Not Reject H ₀
	Teachers		0.258	<.001	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Difference is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)*

Therefore, the learners and parents somehow have the same level of knowledge towards distance learning, while teachers are the most knowledgeable among the three

stakeholders. This is because the teachers are one of the implementers of distance learning.

Teachers must understand the nature of teaching and learning at a distance (Merkley et al., 1997). Northrup (1998) and Moore and Kearsley (1996), As cited in Simonson et al. (2019), teaching at a distance requires instructional delivery methods different from those used in traditional classrooms because the structure of teaching is fundamentally changed.

In relation, most teachers have immediately prepared for teaching remotely when the working-from-home policy has been implemented so that they can be categorized as early adopters of distance learning. Teachers' agility in adopting distance learning during the crisis raises an optimistic signal to effectively adapt and adopt remote instruction to formal school environments in the future (Rahmadi, 2021).

Table 7.2. Test of Difference Between the Attitude of the Stakeholders Towards Distance Learning

Variable	F	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Attitude of the Stakeholders Towards Distance Learning	13.284	2, 417	<.001	Significant	Reject H ₀

The difference is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 7.2 expresses the test of the difference between the attitudes of the stakeholders towards distance learning. The result unveiled that there is a significant difference between the stakeholders' attitudes towards distance learning, $F(2, 417)=13.284, p<.001$, thus, reject the null hypothesis. This infers that stakeholder do not hold the same attitude towards distance learning.

This result is to the study of Nasser and Abouchedid (2000), which revealed that school directors were negative about the possibility that distance education meeting the training needs of school teachers. On the other hand, teachers held a more positive view of distance education. They reported willingness to put forth the effort needed to familiarize themselves with the new technologies and practices.

Similarly, Ojo and Olakulehin's (2006) study showed that students generally hold a positive perception and attitude towards ODL compared to traditional forms of higher education.

In addition, Bordeos (2021) indicated that students faced numerous challenges in using the said modality in learning. Thus, students had a negative attitude toward implementing Modular Distance Learning and perceived it as having a negative effect on their learning experience and motivation to learn.

Post hoc comparisons indicated that among the perception of the respondents, learners' attitude towards distance learning ($M = 3.000$, $SD = 0.491$) is significantly different compared to that of the parents ($M = 3.162$, $SD = 0.426$) and teachers ($M = 3.290$, $SD = 0.353$). This means that the learners and parents do not have the same level of positive attitude towards distance learning, including the teachers versus learners. It is shown in the table that the parents and teachers have the same positive attitude towards distance learning. This further explains that the teachers hold the most favorable attitude towards learning, having the highest mean.

Post Hoc Comparisons

Variable	Respondents		Mean Difference	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Attitude of the Stakeholders Towards Distance Learning	Parents	Teachers	0.127	0.096	Not Significant	Do Not Reject H_0
		Learners	0.162	0.004	Significant	Reject H_0
	Teachers		0.290	<.001	Significant	Reject H_0

**Difference is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)*

Kolak, Markic, Horvat, Klemencic, and Stojanac (2021) stated that the coronavirus pandemic has placed all pupils, along with their parents, in a comfortable home setting and made apparent the advantages and shortcomings of this form of education. The advantages and shortcomings are evident at all levels and in all directions.

With this, it is up to the stakeholders how they will approach the pros and cons of distance learning. This can be reinforced by the Theory of Attitude Change which emphasizes that people try to maintain consistency, congruity, or balance in their attitudes towards something. A person with a negative feeling about a certain thing is likely to feel uncomfortable and will try to resolve the conflict by changing his emotions in an unfavorable direction, rejecting the information, or reinterpreting the information so that it seems less negative. In the results, what's more important is that the stakeholders display a positive attitude toward distance learning, for attitude has a crucial influence on how an individual will go about things in life.

Table 7.3. Test of Difference Between the Stakeholders' Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning

Variable	F	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Stakeholders' Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning	4.574	2, 417	0.011	Significant	Reject H_0

**Difference is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)*

Table 7.3 discloses the test of the difference between the perception of the stakeholders in their level of knowledge towards distance learning. The result divulged that there is a significant difference between the stakeholders' satisfaction towards distance learning, $F(2,417)=4.574$, $p<.011$, thus reject the null hypothesis. This reveals that each stakeholder has a different level of satisfaction towards distance learning.

Post hoc comparisons indicated that among the respondents' perception, learners' level of satisfaction towards distance learning ($M = 3.396$, $SD = 0.462$) is significantly different compared to that of the teachers ($M = 3.577$, $SD = 0.382$). This signifies that the parents and learners have the same level of satisfaction towards distance learning; however, the teachers' level of satisfaction is not the same as the learners' Research has shown that teacher satisfaction and student satisfaction has positively correlated to student academic achievement (McWherter, 2012).

Post Hoc Comparisons

Variable	Respondents		Mean Difference	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Stakeholders' Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning	Parents	Teachers	0.147	0.056	Not Significant	Do Not Reject H_0
		Learners	0.034	0.793	Not Significant	Do Not Reject H_0
	Teachers		0.181	0.013	Significant	Reject H_0

**Difference is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)*

In the study of McWherter (2012), Maslow's theories were used to determine possible significant relationships to satisfaction levels for teachers and students. The decision to utilize the hierarchy of needs for this process was based on Maslow's premises that supporting and satisfying a person's basic needs will allow him/her to reach higher levels of safety and security, love and belonging, esteem, and self-actualization, and with that greater personal achievement.

Table 8.1. Test of Relationship Between the Stakeholders' Level of Knowledge and Their Attitude Towards Distance Learning

Variable	r	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Level of Knowledge and Attitude Towards Distance Learning	0.656	418	<.001	Significant	Reject H_0

**Correlation is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)*

This deduces that the stakeholders' level of knowledge could affect their attitude towards distance learning. Therefore, if the stakeholders are knowledgeable about distance learning, they will most likely have a positive attitude towards it. This conclusion is evident in the data results of this study.

In the literature, most studies conducted in Asia indicate the significant influence of knowledge on attitude formation. The study of Zhu and Xie (2015) agrees with the results of this study which posited that attitude certainty, which indexes the level of confidence or validity an individual attaches to his or her attitude, positively correlates with the amount of knowledge on which an attitude is formed. This means one's knowledge influences his/her attitude towards a particular object or situation.

Table 8.2. Test of Relationship Between the Stakeholders' Attitude and Level of Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning

Variable	r	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Attitude and Satisfaction Towards Distance Learning	0.562	418	<.001	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlation is significant at 0.05 (2-tailed)*

Table 8.2 exposes the test of relationship between the stakeholders' attitude and level of satisfaction towards distance learning. The result revealed that the relationship between the stakeholders' attitude and level of satisfaction towards distance learning is statistically significant, $r(418)=0.562$, $p<.001$; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

This connotes that stakeholders' attitude could influence their level of satisfaction towards distance learning. In this study, the respondents' attitudes regarding affective, cognitive, and behavioral aspects were assessed, revealing a positive attitude towards distance learning. The stakeholders showed a positive disposition and are in congruence with their results in the level of satisfaction in which it was revealed that they are very satisfied.

This study's result was in opposition to the published article by Ahmed (2021) that presented data on the attitude of stakeholders towards distance learning. It showed that the teachers' attitude towards distance learning was negative. They expressed anxiety, worry, apathy, reluctance, and even despair for various reasons with the same with the parents who were particularly sharp and negative towards distance learning; most were not satisfied with the distance learning process.

However, the concepts are parallel to each other, and it was thoroughly explained that if a person has a positive attitude towards something, they will more likely be satisfied or achieve higher academic performance.

DISCUSSION

The study underscores the essential need to understand how stakeholders perceive distance learning by examining their levels of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction as implemented in the public schools of the Guindulman District during the

school year 2021 to 2022. Using a descriptive survey design, the research assessed the relationships and significant differences among these key variables through a four-part survey questionnaire that captured respondents' demographic profiles and their perspectives on distance learning. Adapted from previous related studies and refined to align with the research objectives, the instrument was administered through convenience sampling to a total of 420 participants composed of 168 parents, 168 learners, and 84 teachers who served as the primary stakeholders. The researcher personally visited each school to distribute the questionnaires and allotted three to four weeks for their completion. After retrieval, all responses were systematically processed, collated, and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. By providing empirical insights into how stakeholders experience and evaluate distance learning, the study contributes to strengthening evidence-based educational planning and ensuring that future learning modalities remain responsive to the needs, perceptions, and satisfaction levels of the school community.

Findings

This section presents the results of the study on the stakeholders' level of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction towards distance learning as implemented in the public schools of the Guindulman District during the school year 2021 to 2022. The findings are organized according to the specific objectives of the study, covering the profile of teachers, parents, and learners, their assessments on knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction toward distance learning, and the differences and relationships among these key variables.

1. The profile of the teacher-respondents showed that most educators belonged to the age group of 41 to 50 years old, accounting for 38.09 percent, while only one teacher was 61 years old and above. The data further revealed that the teaching force was predominantly female at 78.57 percent. In terms of educational attainment, a large proportion had earned units in a master's degree, while only a small number had completed a full master's program, and none had reached doctoral-level studies. With respect to teaching experience, the highest percentage was recorded among teachers with 6 to 10 years in service, while the lowest proportions were those with 16 to 20 years and 21 years and above.
2. The parent-respondents' profile indicated that the most common age group was 31 to 40 years old at 36.91 percent, while the youngest group, those below 30 years old, comprised the smallest proportion. Similar to the teachers' profile, females outnumbered males, representing 71.43 percent of the respondents. Regarding educational attainment, more than one-third of parents completed secondary education, while only a small portion finished elementary level. Employment data revealed that the majority were unemployed, whereas business ownership ranked the lowest among the stated occupations.

3. Among learner-respondents, the largest group consisted of those aged 11 to 12 years old at 39.29 percent, while the least represented were those aged 13 to 14. Female learners outnumbered their male counterparts, comprising 62.50 percent of the total. In terms of grade level, elementary pupils represented the majority compared to junior high school students.
4. The respondents' assessment of the stakeholders' level of knowledge toward distance learning resulted in an overall weighted mean of 3.58, interpreted as highly knowledgeable. This indicates that stakeholders possessed substantial understanding of distance learning processes and requirements during its implementation.
5. Stakeholders' attitude towards distance learning was assessed across affective, cognitive, and behavioral domains. The affective dimension obtained an average weighted mean of 3.09, interpreted as somehow positive. The cognitive domain achieved a mean of 2.99, similarly reflecting a somewhat positive outlook. The behavioral domain received the highest mean at 3.37, interpreted as strongly agree, suggesting that stakeholders demonstrated positive and supportive behaviors toward the modality.
6. With respect to satisfaction, the stakeholders expressed high levels of contentment toward distance learning. Satisfaction regarding teacher performance yielded an overall weighted mean of 3.44, interpreted as very satisfied. The same rating was observed in terms of interaction, with a mean of 3.44. Learning assessment garnered an even higher average of 3.52, likewise interpreted as very satisfied, indicating strong approval of how learning progress and outcomes were evaluated.
7. Tests of difference revealed that significant variations existed in the stakeholders' level of knowledge, attitude, and satisfaction when grouped according to their classifications. This suggests that teachers, parents, and learners did not share the same levels of understanding, perspectives, and satisfaction concerning distance learning, highlighting diverse experiences among the three groups.
8. The test of relationship showed that the stakeholders' level of knowledge and their attitude toward distance learning were significantly related. This implies that increased understanding of distance learning corresponded with more positive attitudes. Additionally, results revealed a significant relationship between stakeholders' attitude and their level of satisfaction, indicating that positive attitudes toward distance learning were associated with higher levels of satisfaction with the modality.

Conclusions

It has been concluded in this study that the stakeholders' level of knowledge about this new learning modality has been associated with the attitude they exhibit. Along with this, their attitude has also been found to be related to the amount of satisfaction they

gain. Coherently, suppose a stakeholder has adequate knowledge about distance learning. In that case, he/she will more likely have a positive attitude towards it. If stakeholders have a positive attitude towards distance learning, they will probably be more satisfied. To sum it up, stakeholders have sufficient knowledge and a relatively positive attitude towards distance learning, leading to teacher, parent, and learner satisfaction.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested for consideration based on the study's conclusions and findings:

1. Strengthening Module Distribution and Learning Support Systems. The Department of Education may create and distribute additional module booklets and deploy more Learning Support Aides to assist teachers in the distribution and retrieval of learning materials. This recommendation is especially relevant in schools with seven or fewer teachers, where the workforce is insufficient. Providing additional support will allow teachers more time to conduct home visits for learners struggling with independent learning and to carry out other tasks essential to student welfare.

2. Enhancing Classroom Facilities for Distance Learning. Teachers may invest in improving their classrooms, facilities, and equipment to better support distance learning. Strengthening the learning environment contributes to a more positive attitude among parents and learners and ensures that the needs of students are adequately addressed during remote learning.

3. Encouraging Active Parental Involvement as Home-Learning Facilitators. Parents, who now serve as home-learning facilitators or “para-teachers,” may strengthen their involvement in their children’s education by allotting sufficient time for guidance and assistance. Their consistent support, monitoring, and encouragement play a vital role in sustaining learners’ motivation and success in distance learning.

4. Promoting Learners’ Responsibility and Cooperation in the Learning Process. Learners may coordinate closely with both teachers and parents by submitting weekly learning outputs on time, dedicating adequate time to understand the lessons in the modules, and participating actively in learning assessments. These practices reflect their responsibility and are essential to achieving a productive and successful school year.

5. Guiding Future Research for Continuous Improvement. Future researchers may use the findings of this study as a foundation for related research endeavors. They may also explore the effectiveness of training programs in enhancing teachers’ performance in the new normal, contributing to the ongoing development of instructional practices in distance learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured adherence to ethical standards by first securing formal approval from the concerned school authorities prior to data collection. Informed consent was obtained from all teacher, parent, and learner participants, who were clearly informed of the study's purpose and procedures. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents were assured of their right to decline or withdraw from the study at any point without any negative consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly observed by not collecting any personal identifiers, and all information gathered was treated with utmost privacy. The data were utilized exclusively for academic and research purposes, ensuring that the rights, dignity, and welfare of all participants were fully protected throughout the conduct of the study.

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